

Strengthening 316L austenitic steel through a bimodal approach with ODS steel

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Abstract

Achieving a balance between strength and ductility has long been a challenge in materials science. Strategies such as bimodal grain size distribution have been proposed to overcome this limitation by combining coarse grains for ductility with fine grains for strength. This study presents a novel approach to preparing bimodal 316L austenitic stainless steel, integrating fine-grained oxide dispersion-strengthened (ODS) steel as the strengthening matrix with coarse-grained austenite steel. The fine-grained ODS phase, prepared by mechanical alloying, provides uniform microstructural properties and controls the overall alloy structure. The tensile properties of the bimodal structures were analyzed, revealing that a volume fraction of 70–80% fine grains achieves optimal strength-ductility synergy, deviating from the conventional Hall-Petch relationship. This innovative use of ODS steel demonstrates its potential to enhance mechanical performance and scalability, offering a versatile tool for tailoring advanced austenitic steels.

Keywords

austenitic steel; ODS austenitic steel; bimodal steel; mechanical alloying; spark plasma sintering; mechanical properties; Hall-Petch relation

1. Introduction

The interplay between strength and ductility represents a core challenge in materials science, often requiring trade-offs that limit material performance. Ma [1] introduced strategies that use microstructural design, including bimodal grain size distribution, to overcome this limitation, increase strain hardening, and delay the onset of plastic instability. In such bimodal systems, coarse grains (CG) facilitate ductility by accommodating plastic deformation, while fine grains (FG) contribute to high strength by preventing dislocation motion. The bimodal approach, further elaborated by Flipon [2] and Wu [3], emphasizes the key role of grain size distribution and spatial arrangement. Flipon demonstrated that clusters or isolated CGs significantly affect strain localization, while Wu emphasized the importance of sufficient spacing of domains and strain gradients to enhance work hardening. These principles provide a path for designing materials that effectively overcome the strength and ductility trade-off. Austenitic steel with its inherent ductility resulting from its face-centered crystal structure (FCC) is well suited for investigating bimodal microstructures. The choice of inherently ductile alloy for microstructure optimization studies can more effectively address the problem of maintaining adequate plasticity while significantly increasing strength.

Several approaches of the preparation of bimodal microstructures based on powder metallurgy have been explored. Fujiwara [4] developed a nano/meso hybrid structure in SUS316L steel by mechanically milled steel powder particles densified by hot roll sintering (HRS). The prepared microstructure was heterogeneous formed of shells with work-hardened coarse grains in the core surrounded by nano-grains. The HRS steels demonstrated superior strength and good elongation. However, the formation of a brittle sigma (σ) phase and the need for precise control of the shell-to-core ratio were found to be drawbacks limiting the scalability of the process. Further problems with the milling-based approach were highlighted by Fujiwara [5], who reported the formation of nano-ferrite grains during long-term mechanical milling of SUS316L steel. This deformation transformation of the austenite phase to the nano-ferrite phase created heterogeneities that impair ductility and microstructural stability. Zheng [6] extended the latter work by designing a harmonic structure in SUS316L steel using high-energy ball milling followed by hot isostatic pressing (HIP). Ultrafine-grained (UFG) shells with coarse-grained (CG) cores reduced strain localization, increasing strain hardening and uniform elongation. Nevertheless, an achievement of the optimal balance of mechanical properties was limited by the small content of large grains derived from the deformation of the starting powders during milling. The above examples highlight existing compromises related to milling-based methods, particularly with respect to phase control and grain uniformity.

The next approach of the bimodal microstructure preparation via the Bimodal Milling (BiM) process was proposed by Sharma [7]. The key principle was the simultaneous milling of coarse and fine SUS316L steel powder resulting in granules of large particles covered with fine particles. Consequent consolidation by spark plasma sintering (SPS) produced hierarchically structured materials with excellent strength and ductility by achieving controlled shell thickness and spatial distribution of grains. The shortcoming of the BiM process was an induction of γ to α/α' phase transformations in the fine grain shell during milling. An insufficient recovery of α/α' phase during sintering then degraded ductility of the steel. Flipon [8] studied the mechanical properties of AISI 316L bimodal steel prepared by SPS. They combined UFG powders obtained by ball milling with CG powders to produce a controlled bimodal microstructure. The presence of CG in the UFG matrix of the steel improved the ductility by enhancing the strain-hardening mechanisms and reducing the stress concentration. The SPS consolidation process allowed precise grain size control and minimized grain growth during sintering, resulting in improved strength and ductility balance then for unimodal microstructures. However, oxide formation and the need for strict process control remained significant problems.

This study proposes a new approach to overcome the trade-off between strength and ductility in austenitic stainless steel by using oxide dispersion-strengthened steel (ODS) as a fine-grained component in a bimodal microstructure. The high strength of nanoscale oxide particles and grain growth resistance make ODS steel an ideal fine-grained matrix. This approach aligns with the theoretical requirements for bimodal microstructures outlined by Flipon and Wu, who emphasized the importance of domain spacing to facilitate the accumulation of dislocations and strain gradients, which enhances the strengthening of the bimodal steel.

2. Materials and methods

To investigate the mechanical properties of bimodal 316L austenitic steels, powders were prepared by mixing fine ODS and coarse austenite powder and compacted using spark plasma sintering. The starting powder used for preparing both fine and coarse-grain steel was AISI 316L steel gas-atomized powder with a powder particle size of 15-38 μm and $d_{50}=27.6 \mu\text{m}$ (Sandvik Osprey Ltd., United Kingdom). The fine ODS 316L powder was prepared by mechanical alloying of starting 316L powder with Ti and Y (composition provided in **Table 1**), and the process was realized in 100 g batches that were alloyed using a planetary ball mill (Pulverisette P-6, Fritsch, Germany). The milling was done in a hardened steel vial (tool die steel 62SiMnCr4, EN 1.2101) with 25.4 mm steel balls (bearing steel 100Cr6, EN 1.3505) for

24 h under vacuum. The ball-to-powder ratio was 15:1, and the revolutions of the central disc were set to 350 rpm. The produced powder was mechanically sieved into the fraction with particle size $<50\mu\text{m}$. No oxygen source was intentionally added during the preparation of the powders. The primary sources included surface oxidation of powders during handling, residual oxygen in the milling atmosphere, and the high reactivity of alloying elements such as Ti and Y, which carry native oxide layers.

Table 1 Chemical composition of the feedstock powder batch used for ODS 316L steel powder preparation by mechanical alloying.

Element	Feedstock powders			Composition of powder batch
	Purity (%)	Particle size (μm)	Manufacturer	(wt.%)
316L	-	15-38	Sandvik Osprey	99.46
Ti	99.7	150	Sigma-Aldrich	0.3
Y	99.5	400	Sigma-Aldrich	0.24

A total of 5 blends of powders were prepared, namely the pure starting coarse powder, pure fine ODS powder and 3 mixtures of powders containing 70 wt.%, 75 wt.% and 80 wt.% of fine ODS powder and the corresponding amount of starting coarse powder (composition of blends prepared is provided in **Table 2**). Mixing powders was done by simply shaking the powders in the container.

Table 2 Compositions of powder blends used for bimodal austenitic steel preparation together with their oxygen content prior to the consolidation.

Blend/steel label	Powder		Oxygen content (wt. %)
	fine ODS austenite (wt. %)	coarse austenite (wt. %)	
ODS0	0	100	0.0504
ODS70	70	30	0.9423
ODS75	75	25	0.9091
ODS80	80	20	0.9271
ODS100	100	0	1.3029
powder of 316L steel (ODS0)			0.0504
powder of 316L ODS steel prior milling			0.0531
powder of 316L ODS steel after 24h of milling			0.2238
fine-grained powder of 316L ODS steel after 24h of milling (ODS100)			1.3029

All powder blends were compacted into cylindrical pellets ($\phi 30 \times 6$ mm) using SPS at 1150 °C, 80 MPa pressure, with a dwell time of 20 min and a heating/cooling rate of 100 °C/min (SPS, TT SPS 10-4, Thermal Technology LLC, USA). The density of the steels was determined by

double weighing using the Archimedes method in deionized water and air, following the EN 623-2 standard.

Flat dog-bone-shaped tensile specimens with a nominal cross-section of $3 \times 1 \text{ mm}^2$ and a gauge length of 14 mm were machined from the sintered compacts using electro-discharge machining. The entire surface of the tensile specimens was polished to a mirror surface finish by $1 \mu\text{m}$ diamond paste. Tensile tests were then conducted at room temperature at a cross-head speed of 0.1 mm/s (corresponding to a strain rate $1 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$) following the ISO 6892-1:2016 standard (Z50, Zwick/Roell, Germany). Vickers hardness of the compacted steels was determined according to EN ISO 6507 standard using a ZHU0.2 instrumented hardness tester (Zwick/Roell, Germany) at a load of $\sim 50 \text{ N}$. The hardness was measured on samples extracted from the pellets in the circumferential direction and hot mounted in conductive epoxy resin. The surface for hardness measurement was prepared by standard metallographic techniques by grinding and polishing with diamond abrasive up to $\frac{1}{4} \mu\text{m}$ grain size. At least 10 valid indentations were made for each pellet.

The microstructure and chemical composition of the compacted steels were observed using a scanning electron microscope LYRA 3 XMU FEG/SEM FIB (Tescan, Czech Republic) equipped with both EBSD and EDS detectors and operated by the software Aztec (Oxford Instruments, UK). The samples, both for SEM and EBSD analysis, were extracted in the same orientation as samples used for hardness measurement (circumferential direction) and hot mounted in conductive epoxy resin. The samples were metallographically prepared by grinding on sandpapers up to grind size P2500 and polishing with diamond pastes up to $\frac{1}{4} \mu\text{m}$. Final polishing was conducted in the vibratory polisher VibroMet 2 (Buehler) in colloidal suspension of silica particles of mean size $0.04 \mu\text{m}$ for 24 hours. The microstructural observation in SEM was realized in the backscatter electron mode (BSE) at an acceleration voltage of 20 kV. The size and volume content of oxide particles in the steels were quantitatively analysed from three different areas of size $13 \times 10 \mu\text{m}^2$ of the sample using the image analysis in the software J-image.

The microstructures of the compacted steels were also analysed by means of transmission electron microscopy (TEM). The transmission electron microscope Talos F200i (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Czech Republic), equipped with a Super-X G2 EDS detector operated at 200 kV, was used. The lamella for the TEM was prepared using a focusing ion beam (FIB) (Helios NanoLab 660, FEI, Czech Republic). The size and volume content of oxide particles at the grain boundaries and in the grain interior of the TEM images were quantitatively analysed from different areas of FIB lamella of size $3 \times 3 \mu\text{m}^2$ using image analysis.

The grain microstructure of the steels was characterized by analysis of EBSD data. The EBSD data were acquired with a resolution varying from 1.25 μm to 0.05 μm at an acceleration voltage of 20kV. The grain size (GS) distribution was determined from the EBSD data by recognizing the grain boundaries as high-angle boundaries at the angle limit value of 15°. The special grain boundaries representing twins were not taken as high-angle grain boundaries even if they exceeded 15°. The grain size of unimodal steels with coarse and fine grain was quantified from the maps of area 650×490 μm^2 and 13×10 μm^2 , respectively. The grain sizes of the coarse and fine phases of bimodal steel variants (ODS70, ODS75, ODS80) were quantified separately owing to their significant difference. The grain size of the fine phase was determined from the areas within the only fine-grained fraction (matrix) of the bimodal microstructure from the maps of area 13×10 μm^2 . The grain size of the coarse phase was determined from the only areas containing a coarse-grained fraction of bimodal microstructure from the maps of area 130×100 μm^2 . In each case, the mean grain size was determined as an area-weighted grain size from three maps acquired from different sample locations. The representative (overall) average grain size of the bimodal microstructure of all blended variants was calculated by the rule of mixtures using volume fractions of fine and coarse areas and corresponding mean grain sizes. Fractography analysis of fracture surfaces of tensile specimens was done using a scanning electron microscopy LYRA 3 XMU FEG/SEM FIB (Tescan, Czech Republic).

The phase composition of the compacted steels was determined using an X-ray powder diffractometer (Rigaku SmartLab 3 kW CF2; Rigaku, Japan) in the Bragg-Brentano geometry, using Cu-K α radiation (40 kV, 30 mA) for a scanning 2 θ range between 10° and 100° and a scanning speed of 3°/min. The surface of the samples for XRD analyses was prepared by metallography grinding up to a grid size of P2500.

The oxygen content of the consolidated steels was determined via the inert gas fusion technique using an elemental analyzer TC-336 (Leco, USA).

The initial volume fractions of coarse and fine powders described above were estimated using FEM simulations of bimodal microstructures. The numerical simulations were performed using the software Z-set. The 2D model is shown in **Fig. 1**. The microstructure was prepared by the software Neper using Voronoi tessellation with predefined seeds for each grain. The coarse grains' diameter was set to be 10 times larger than the fine grains' diameter. The number of seeds for coarse grains sets the volume fractions of fine/coarse grains. Altogether, nine different volume fractions were prepared, ranging from 30% to 90% of small grains. The finite element mesh was made of around 48,000 linear 2D triangular elements. The boundary conditions represent uniaxial tension with plane strain conditions, and they are schematically shown in

Fig. 1. The right side edge remains straight, but it can move along X direction. These boundary conditions mimic the loading of the inner volume of material. The constitutive behavior of the material consisted of isotropic elasticity and von Mises plasticity. Data for the model are obtained directly from the experimental tensile curves of pure fine and coarse-grained materials (see **Fig. 10**). The experimental curves were converted into true stress-true plastic strain format.

Fig. 1. 2D model of bimodal microstructure with 50 % volume fraction of fine grains used in FEM simulations. The boundary conditions for uniaxial loading are prescribed at each side of the modelled domain.

3. Results

The results of the FEM analysis of bimodal microstructures are shown in **Fig 2**. The yield stress (YS) is determined at the onset of plasticity. The ultimate tensile stress (UTS) is estimated using the Considère criterion (hardening modulus is equal to strength). Elongation is taken as the uniaxial strain at the UTS point. The results show that for the volume fraction of fine grains between 70 – 80 %, materials embody larger elongation, which is manifested by departing from the typical strength-uniform elongation trend. Therefore, this volume fraction range was selected for the experimental study. Similar results were obtained by Flippon [2].

Fig 2. Elongation vs stress results obtained from FEM simulations of bimodal structures with different volume fractions of fine grains.

The XRD analysis presented in **Fig. 3** revealed that the phase composition of the unimodal and bimodal steels was consistent across all samples, with a primary structure of austenite (γ , FCC). However, trace amounts of residual ferrite (α , BCC) were also identified. Nevertheless, the presence of residual ferrite in the XRD analyses was probably caused by an insufficient samples preparation process, which finished on grinding with the grid size P2500. In the case of EBSD analysis with a dedicated metallography preparation process, including also polishing no ferrite content in the microstructure of the steels was found (see further). The ferrite could probably appear in the subsurface location of the samples as a result of deformation transformation from the austenitic phase which was also observed by Fujiwara [5].

Fig. 3. XRD patterns of dense unimodal and bimodal austenitic steels.

The examples of microstructures of consolidated unimodal and bimodal steels are shown in **Fig. 4**. The microstructure of the CG variant of the steel ODS0 was formed by large austenitic grains containing the oxide particles. The presence of oxide particles in the microstructures of all prepared steels was caused by their relatively high oxygen content. The results of the combustion analysis of the powders prior to sintering are given in **Table 2**. The origin of oxygen content in the steels came principally from two sources: i) powder manipulation and ii) ball-milling process. The starting powder of 316L steel contained 0.0504 wt.% of oxygen. The addition of Ti and Y into the starting powder of 316L steel increased the oxygen content by about 0.0027 wt.% as a result of the enrichment of reactive elements with native oxide layers. After 24 h of mechanical alloying in vacuum, the oxygen content in the milled powder increased to 0.2238 wt.%. The difference between the two latter oxygen concentrations is considered to be the oxygen content introduced by the ball milling process. The separated fine-grained powder with particle size $<50 \mu\text{m}$, prepared from milled powder by sieving, contained a significantly higher amount of oxygen, 1.3029 wt.%. Thus, the amount of the oxygen content caused by powder manipulation and separation, e.g. by the grain refining procedure step, is considered to be approximately 1.07 wt.%. These results suggest that powder manipulation and separation of fine-grained powder are the most significant sources of oxygen in the prepared powder of 316L ODS steel. The high oxygen content in ODS100 steel ($\sim 1.30\%$ wt.%) can be attributed to the use of reactive elements (Ti and Y) with surface oxides; milling under vacuum without inert gas washing; and the lack of post-milling reduction or degassing treatment. While the oxygen content is higher than standard values, it resulted in effective dispersion strengthening and did not hinder consolidation. The oxygen contents measured in ODS70

(0.9423 wt.%) and ODS75 (0.9091 wt.%) do not strictly follow the increasing trend expected with increasing fine ODS powder content. This discrepancy can be attributed to the low-energy mixing method (simple shaking), which may lead to local inhomogeneities in powder blends, especially for small batches. In addition, the small difference (~ 0.03 wt.%) is within the measurement uncertainty of the LECO analysis technique and is not considered statistically significant. The results of local chemical analysis (EDS) of the matrix and particles in the microstructure of the steels are shown in **Table 3**. The largest particles in the microstructure of CG steel were found to be Si-rich oxides with size up to several μm and about two times smaller particles of Si-Mn-rich oxides. The Si-rich and Si-Mn-rich oxide particles were located both at the grain boundaries and inside the grains. The average diameter of oxide particles and their volume fractions obtained by image analysis were determined to be 302 nm and 0.8 %, respectively.

The FG variant of the steel ODS100 was composed from very fine austenitic grains with a large volume content of much finer oxide particles than in the case of CG steel ODS0. The high content of oxygen particles in the ODS100 steel is significantly related to high oxygen content and the addition of alloying elements of yttrium and titan. The TEM microstructure of the ODS100 is shown in **Fig. 5**. Due to relatively high oxygen content, the ODS steel contained several types of oxide particles. The results of EDS analysis in TEM revealed that these oxide particles were rich in Mn-Si-Y-Ti, Cr-Mn-Si-Y-Ti, Cr-Mn-Y-Ti and Y-Ti. The size ranges of those oxide particles are given in **Table 3**.

The smallest oxide particles were rich in Y-Ti and their dominant location of observation was grain interior. The other types of oxide particles enriched principally in Cr, Mn and Si were observed at grain boundaries or their surroundings. Due to their complex chemical composition, those larger oxide particles probably nucleated at the locations of previously created Y-Ti-rich oxide particles. The average diameter of the finest population of oxide particles rich in Y-Ti-O and their volume fractions obtained by image analysis were determined 53.2 nm and 4.3 %, respectively.

The microstructures of bimodal alloys, derived from mixtures of CG and FG metal powders and their consolidation, followed the main microstructural features of both CG and FG steels, i.e. both fine-grained and coarse-grained areas and small and large presence of oxide particles. At the interfaces of FG and CG phases a very good metallurgical connection and significant difference in the content of oxide particles was observed as shown in **Fig. 4**. In addition, the occurrence of larger Mn-Si-Y-Ti-rich and Cr-Mn-Y-Ti-rich oxides at the interfaces were detected.

Fig. 4. The SEM microstructures of unimodal steels ODS0 and ODS100 and bimodal steel ODS80 observed in BSE mode.

Table 3: Chemical composition of analysed locations of a matrix of ODS0, ODS80 and ODS100 steels and of the particles in SEM/EDS and TEM/EDS together with their size range.

Spectrum Analysed	Element (wt. %)										Phase description	Size range (nm)
	Fe	Cr	Ni	Mo	Mn	Si	Y	Ti	O	C		
1	67.4	18.0	10.1	2.4	1.4	0.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	matrix	
2	37.6	11.3	4.8	1.1	1.0	20.2	0.2	0.0	23.8	0.0	Si-O	610 – 5320
3	38.5	12.6	4.5	3.6	13.2	9.1	0.0	0.1	18.6	0.0	Mn-Si-O	190 – 1730
4	69.2	16.8	10.3	2.2	0.8	0.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	matrix CG	
5	67.5	16.9	9.7	2.2	1.4	0.7	0.3	0.3	1.1	0.0	matrix FG	
6	53.4	16.9	7.0	1.4	3.1	5.1	0.4	0.6	12.2	0.0	Mn-Si-Y-Ti-O	138 – 678
7	55.2	19.4	7.5	1.6	4.7	0.9	0.4	0.9	9.5	0.0	Cr-Mn-Y-Ti-O	94 – 257
8	67.4	16.1	9.5	2.4	1.1	0.5	0.5	0.5	1.7	0.0	matrix FG	
9	42.8	14.0	5.9	1.7	4.0	8.8	3.9	1.1	17.7	0.0	Mn-Si-Y-Ti-O	138 – 678
10	6.2	33.1	1.2	0.7	20.3	3.1	0.8	5.9	28.3	0.3	Cr-Mn-Si-Y-Ti-O	116 – 598
11	6.1	34.2	1.1	0.7	20.3	0.6	2.0	6.2	28.4	0.3	Cr-Mn-Y-Ti-O	94 – 257
12	58.7	12.6	4.2	0.4	1.3	0.7	4.1	5.2	12.6	0.2	Y-Ti-O	26 – 114

Fig. 5. The TEM microstructure of unimodal ODS steel ODS100.

The results of EBSD analysis confirmed that the microstructure of all prepared steels is composed of austenite. No ferrite content, contrary to XRD analysis, was detected. The results of grain size analyses of the steels with various contents of fine and coarse-grained fractions are given in **Table 4**. The inverse pole figures (IPF) maps of the grain microstructure of selected variants of the steel are shown in **Fig. 6**. The unimodal steel with coarse and fine grains attained mean grain sizes of 41.1 μm (ODS0) and 1.0 μm (ODS100), respectively. The grain size of unimodal fine-grained steel was refined by a factor of 41. In the bimodal variants of the steel (ODS70, ODS75, ODS80), the coarse-grained fraction of grains was considerably refined compared to the unimodal coarse-grained variant as their mean sizes varied from 9.8 μm to 10.8 μm . In contrast, the mean grain size of fine-grained fraction in bimodal steels remained very similar to its unimodal counterpart, i.e., 0.9–1.1 μm . Thus the aspect ratio of coarse and fine grain size areas achieved for bimodal steels was approximately 10. It can be noticed that the grain size of the large-grained fraction of bimodal variants is approximately 3 times smaller than the size of input (starting) powder particles ($d_{50}=27.6 \mu\text{m}$) used for the initial mixtures of the powders prior to their consolidation. Thus, it can be derived that the one powder particle of starting powder was composed of several grains. Hadraba [9], in the previous study, derived similar results in which the relation between the size of the input powder particles and prior austenite grain size of the 9Cr steel undergoing mechanical alloying was obtained. Considering the mean grain size of unimodal steel with coarse grains (ODS0) 41.1 μm , significantly smaller

the mean grain size of coarse-grained fraction in bimodal variants (factor of 4) couldn't be affected by the only size of the input powder particles itself. The growth of the grains of the CG phase of bimodal variants was probably limited by the pinning effect of oxide particles at the interface with the FG phase, see **Fig. 6** for ODS80. This can be illustrated in **Fig. 7** where the interface of the CG and FG phase is shown in detail. Limited growth of grains of the CG phase in the bimodal steels is caused by the blocking of grain boundaries via the significantly increased presence of the oxide particles and density of grain boundaries at the interfaces of CG and FG phases. On the contrary, the grain growth in unimodal coarse-grained steel is not limited to the initial powder particle due to the much smaller presence of oxide particles and can proceed through the neighbouring ones, and form larger grains than the size of initial powder particles, see **Fig. 6** for ODS0.

Fig. 6. The IPF maps of the microstructure of the unimodal and bimodal austenitic steels.

Fig. 7. The interface of the coarse and fine grain fractions of bimodal austenitic steel ODS75 visualised by TEM.

The bulk density measurements revealed that the coarse-grained steel sample (ODS0) exhibited the highest density at $7.88 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$, while the fine-grained ODS sample (ODS100) had the lowest density at $7.69 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ (**Table 4**). The 2.5 % lower density of ODS100 is attributed to the presence of a large number of grain boundaries generating crystallographic defects, the presence of light oxide particles, and reduced plasticity of the mechanically alloyed powder caused by milling which limits densification during sintering. This behaviour is consistent with previous findings on the densification of hardened powders [9]. The density of bimodal steels varied nearly linearly with the fraction of fine-grained powder, following the rule of mixtures (R.O.M.). As shown in **Fig. 8**, the bimodal steel densities were 1.4 % to 2.1 % lower than the unimodal coarse-grained steel, depending on the proportions of coarse-grained and fine-grained powders.

Table 4 The mean grain size characteristics and density of unimodal and bimodal steels.

Blend/steel label	Mean grain size				Density ($\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$)
	fine-grained FG ODS austenite (μm)	coarse-grained CG austenite (μm)	CG/FG aspect ratio (-)	representative (overall) average (μm)	
ODS0	-	41.1 ± 3.3	-	41.1	7.88
ODS70	1.0 ± 0.3	10.5 ± 2.5	11	3.8	7.77
ODS75	0.9 ± 0.2	10.8 ± 2.7	12	3.4	7.76
ODS80	1.1 ± 0.3	9.8 ± 2.1	9	2.8	7.71
ODS100	1.0 ± 0.2	-	-	1.0	7.69

Fig. 8. Dependence of density on fine-grained volume fraction for unimodal and bimodal steels. The rule-of-mixtures is provided in the graph.

The mechanical properties of composite materials can be estimated using the Voigt and Reuss equations, which provide the upper and lower bounds for the material's behaviour. These bounds are commonly used to evaluate the contributions of different phases to the overall mechanical properties of heterogeneous materials. The Voigt model assumes uniform strain across all phases, predicting higher strength and stiffness. The mechanical property P of a heterogeneous material is given as a combination of the mechanical properties P_i of the components and their volume fraction v_i :

$$P = \sum_i P_i \cdot v_i. \quad (1)$$

In contrast, the Reuss model assumes uniform stress, resulting in lower strength and higher strain according to the equation:

$$\frac{1}{P} = \sum_i \frac{v_i}{P_i}. \quad (2)$$

The hardness of the prepared steels varied with the volume fraction of fine-grained ODS powder, ranging from 1.46 GPa for the coarse-grained steel (ODS0) to 3.67 GPa for the fine-grained steel (ODS100). As shown in **Fig. 9**, the dependence of hardness on the fine-grained ODS fraction falls between the Voigt and Reuss bounds, indicating a partially coupled system. This behaviour aligns with the explanation proposed by Flippon [8], where a non-negligible coupling between coarse-grained (CG) and ultra-fine-grained (UFG) populations influences the mechanical properties. The interactions between the CG and UFG regions, such as stress

transfer and mechanical confinement, likely enhance the hardness beyond what simple mixture rules predict.

Table 5 The mean values of hardness and tensile properties of unimodal and bimodal austenitic steels. HV is Vickers hardness, YS tensile yield strength, UTS ultimate tensile strength, A_g uniform elongation at UTS, and A total elongation.

Blend/steel label	HV (GPa)	YS (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	A_g (%)	A (%)	A/A_g (-)
ODS0	1.46	260	605	59.8	65.7	1.10
ODS70	2.80	605	874	22.3	22.9	1.03
ODS75	2.86	673	908	19.2	20.7	1.08
ODS80	2.96	654	907	18.5	18.8	1.02
ODS100	3.67	969	1078	14.8	22.8	1.54

Fig. 9. Dependence of hardness on fine-grained volume fraction. The rules-of-mixtures are provided in the graph.

The tensile behaviour of the prepared steels is presented in **Fig. 10**. The results of tensile testing comprising the yield strength (YS), ultimate tensile strength (UTS), uniform elongation (A_g) and total elongation (A) values are summarized in **Table 5**. The dependences of tensile properties on the coarse-grained volume fraction are illustrated in **Fig. 10**, alongside the rule-of-mixtures bounds of the Voigt and Reuss for comparison. The results revealed that the YS, UTS, and uniform elongation closely follow just the Reuss prediction. Moreover, the total elongation is an exception which does not follow the Reuss prediction. This indicates that the

microstructure of both unimodal and bimodal steels well accommodates the applied loading at uniform stress conditions which is also noticed on true stress-true strain curves of tensile testing, **Fig 10b**. From a micromechanical point of view, these results suggest that also bimodal grain microstructures are well-transferring uniform plastic deformation. In contrast, as discussed previously, the hardness values lie between the Voigt and Reuss bounds. This discrepancy can be attributed to the fact that hardness testing involves a triaxial stress-strain state which in principle cannot be solely described either by the assumption of uniform strain (Voigt) or uniform stress (Reuss) state. The tensile test results showed that the bimodal steels demonstrated an increased scatter of both strength and deformation properties than the unimodal steels, see **Fig. 10** and **Fig. 11**. The increased scatter of tensile properties of the bimodal alloys is likely caused by their greater microstructural variability compared to the unimodal steels mainly owing to the variability of the distribution of the CG phase in the matrix of the FG phase and by the random presence of large oxide particles at their interfaces. The reason for the strong deviation of total elongation results of bimodal steels from the Reuss prediction can be found in their different necking behaviour compared to the unimodal steels. The prepared steels demonstrated different localized deformation behaviour in the necking region which can be related to the ratio of total elongation to uniform elongation which is given in **Table 5**. The highest ratio value of 1.54 and thus the largest non-uniform deformation was achieved by the unimodal ODS steel ODS100. A much smaller ratio value of 1.10 was obtained for unimodal non-ODS steel ODS0 which indicates that the localized plastic deformation of coarse-grained steel is influenced by the presence of oxide particles in its microstructure. The lowest ratio values in the range from 1.02 – 1.08 was determined for bimodal steel suggesting their even lower ability to accommodate the localized plastic deformation.

Fig. 10. Tensile curves of the unimodal and bimodal steels produced: engineering stress-strain curves (a), true stress-true strain curves (b).

Fig. 11. Dependence of YS, UTS and Ag on fine-grained volume fraction (a). Dependence of A on fine-grained volume fraction (b). The rules-of-mixtures are provided in the graphs.

The results of the fractography analysis are shown in **Fig. 12**. The observation revealed ductile fracture micromechanism for both unimodal and bimodal steels. The observation of fracture surfaces coarse-grained steel ODS0 showed rather shallow dimples which were the largest from all prepared variants of steel. At the bottom of dimples number of oxide particles was observed suggesting that the fracture process was substantially affected by the presence of oxide particles. The appearance of fracture of fine-grained steel revealed at larger magnification evenly spaced shear ridges. The shear ridges were composed of very small dimples typical for ODS steel with the presence of fine dispersion of oxide particles. Developed shear ridges indicate smooth and continuous accommodation of microstructure to localized plastic deformation. The fracture surfaces of the bimodal steels contained areas of large dimples embedded in the array composed of very small dimples which are shown in the example of the bimodal alloy ODS80. The fracture surfaces of bimodal alloys correspond to the microstructure mixtures of CG and FG phases. The distinct difference in fracture surfaces of bimodal steels compared to the unimodal steels was partial decohesion of at the interfaces of FG and CG phase.

Fig. 12. Fracture surfaces of tensile specimens of unimodal steels ODS0 and ODS100 and bimodal steel ODS80.

Table 6 The results of calculation of strengthening mechanisms of the unimodal steels ODS0 and ODS100.

	ODS0	ODS100
Grain size (μm)	41.1	1.0
Oxide size (nm)	302	53.2
Volume fraction of oxides (%)	0.8	4.3
Dislocation density (m^{-2})	1.0×10^{13}	1.0×10^{15}
σ_{GB} (MPa)	223	440
σ_{Orowan} (MPa)	23	217
σ_{DS} (MPa)	30	297
$\sigma_{YS} = \sigma_{GB} + \sigma_{Orowan} + \sigma_{DS}$ (MPa)	262	954
Experimental result, YS (MPa)	276	969

The strength of metal alloys is driven by their microstructural features. The overall strengthening can be divided into contributions given by grains boundaries, secondary particles (precipitates and/or nano-oxides particles for ODS alloys) and stored dislocations. The individual contributions can be quantitatively estimated by respective phenomenological models and compared with the experimental results.

Grain boundary strengthening

Grain boundary (GB) strengthening (σ_{GB}) contribution to the yield strength (YS) is estimated by the Hall–Petch relationship, which is given by the relation [10][11]:

$$\sigma_{GB} = \sigma_0 + k_{HP}D^{-1/2} \quad (3),$$

where D is the average grain size; σ_0 represents the yield stress of a single crystal and combines lattice friction stress and solid solution strengthening. Parameter k_{HP} is Hall-Petch constant representing the effects of grain boundaries. The respective values for 316L steels are taken as 183.31 MPa and 253.66MPa respectively according to Wang [12].

Dispersion strengthening

Secondary particles such as precipitates and/or oxide particles, which are not shearable contribute to hardening by the Orowan mechanism. Dislocations are pinned at the particles, bow-out in between up to the creation of Orowan dislocations loops around particles. The level of strengthening (σ_{Orowan}) is given by the size and mutual distance (volume fraction) of particles and it can be described by the Orowan-Ashby equation. The modified Orowan equation is given by the following equation [13]:

$$\sigma_{Orowan} = \frac{0.81M\mu b}{2\pi\sqrt{1-\nu}} \frac{\ln\left(\frac{2\sqrt{\frac{2}{3}}r}{2b}\right)}{\sqrt{\frac{2\pi}{3V_f}r}} \quad (4),$$

where M is the Taylor factor, which is 3.05 [14], μ represents the shear modulus, which is 75 GPa for 316L steel [15]; b represents the Burgers vector, taken as 0.257 nm [16]; ν is Poisson's ratio, which is 0.3 [17]; and r and V_f are the average radius and volume fraction of oxide particles, respectively.

Dislocation strengthening

Dislocation strengthening is based on the dislocation-dislocation interactions where mobile dislocations travel through the forest of dislocations created by the previous fabrication and plastic deformation of a material. The dislocation strengthening (σ_{DS}) is described by the Taylor relationship described by equation [18]:

$$\sigma_{DS} = M\alpha\mu b\sqrt{\rho} \quad (5),$$

where α is an empirical constant, which is 0.16 [19], and ρ is dislocation density. The dislocation density for ODS0 steel is taken as 1×10^{13} which corresponds to cast 316 steel with a similar level of yield strength and grain size [20]. The dislocation density for ODS100

steel is taken as 1×10^{15} , which is a representative value for the ODS version of 316L steel [21].

The results of calculations for each strengthening mechanism of the steels ODS0 and ODS100 are listed in **Table 6**. The yield strength of prepared steels ODS0 and ODS100 is then obtained as the sum of all strengthening mechanisms:

$$\sigma_{YS} = \sigma_{GB} + \sigma_{Orowan} + \sigma_{DS} \quad (6).$$

The comparison of the experimental results and theoretical predictions of the yield strengths is also given in **Table 6**. The theoretical and experimental results of YS are in close agreement with a difference of around 15 MPa.

4. Discussion

The key aspect for obtaining required mechanical properties is the control of microstructure evolution during the manufacturing process. The mechanical alloying with subsequent powder particles sorting via sieving provides such control and results in uniform grain size distribution as shown by Hadraba [9]. The combination of two phases with uniform grain size distributions with different mean grain sizes provides composite effects of high strength and uniform elongation. The comparison of presented materials with results obtained by other authors is illustrated in **Fig. 13**. Flipon [8] employed a simple mixing of milled and un-milled powders, producing SPS-sintered steels with large grains (15 μm) surrounded by fine grains (0.3 μm) and achieved only a moderate composite effect compared to unimodal materials. On the other hand, Sharma [7], Fujiwara [4], and Zheng [6] achieved much stronger effect. However, they applied a more complex fabrication strategy by forming granules or shells with fine grains (ranging from 20 nm to ~ 500 nm) creating a mantle of the coarse-grained cores. Our manufacturing strategy is able to achieve the same level of composite effect as Sharma, Fujiwara and Zheng [7][4][6] with processing simplicity comparable to Flipon [8][8].

The composite effect of bimodal structure arises from the combination of strengthening mechanisms in individual phases. In the fine-grained matrix, all three strengthening mechanisms have the effect of the same order of magnitude. The grain boundary strengthening is the strongest in our case (440 MPa) and comparable to the results of Seils [22] (423 ± 130 MPa). The dispersion strengthening and dislocation forest are also significant contributors with estimated values of 297 MPa and 217 MPa respectively. Strong activation of these three mechanisms ensures very high strength of the fine-grained ODS matrix. The strength can be further improved by altering the characteristics of oxide particles dispersions: increasing

their density [23][22], chemical compositions [24] and/or changing the elastic properties [25]. The coarse-grained phase shows different prominence of strengthening mechanisms. The strongest one is also the grain boundary strengthening (223 MPa) while the other two are the order of magnitude lower (particle dispersion – 23 MPa, dislocations forest – 30 MPa). The low density of secondary particles and dislocations forest provides suitable conditions for dislocation slip with long mean free path which is able to accommodate large amount of plastic deformation. Therefore, bimodal material is able to achieve high strength due to the fine-grain matrix and high elongation due to the action of coarse grains. The grain boundary strengthening is the most significant effect, therefore, the quantification of the composite effect is shown in the classical Hall-Petch representation of yield stress versus grain size. The crucial part in such a representation is the estimation of the average grain size of bimodal microstructure. The simple rule of mixture is used in the present study taking into account the mean grain sizes of individual phases and their respective volume fractions in bimodal microstructure. The results are illustrated in **Fig. 14**. There is a clear improvement in strength with respect to the result of other authors, however, the comparison has to be taken with caution due to the different methods of grain size estimations. Therefore, the Hall-Petch relation combining results for unimodal fine-grained and coarse-grained grain material is created. It represents an intermediate estimate of the Hall-Petch relation between both unimodal materials and allows direct comparison of the mechanical performance of bimodal material with respect to its unimodal components. The improvement yield stress of bimodal materials is about 60 MPa with respect to the Hall-Petch relation showing the synergic effect arising from bimodal microstructure.

Fig. 13 Relationship between yield strength and uniform elongation of 316L stainless steels prepared with various approaches, literature and present study data.

Fig. 14 The Hall-Petch relation of yield strength vs. representative (overall) grain size of prepared steels and its comparison with other 316L stainless steels prepared with various approaches.

The comparison of tensile properties of prepared steels with literature data of purely ODS 316L steels prepared by Shi, Miao and Gao [26][27][28] is given in **Fig. 15**. It can be stated that the

ODS steel ODS100 and the bimodal steels with higher FG fractions ODS75 and ODS80 provide better balance of strength-uniform elongation properties than other ODS 316L steels. Particularly, the ODS steel 316L prepared by Shi Shi2022 achieves a similar tensile curve as the bimodal steel ODS70. Next, the comparison with the literature data points that increasing strength properties of ODS 316L steels are also connected with a decrease of necking (localized) deformation. The same effect was obtained in this study. However, further improvement (an increase) of localized deformation of the bimodal steels could be significantly improvement upon increasing necking deformation of the unimodal steel, thus particularly of the CG steel ODS0 via an improved control of oxygen content.

Fractography examination of fracture surfaces of the bimodal steels discovered that their ductile fracture micromechanism is connected with the decohesion of the interfaces of the fine-grained matrix and of coarse-grained regions. This fracture mechanism involves more intensive plastic deformation between surrounding regions of the CG phase transferred by the FG matrix which should be realized by localized shear deformation, **Fig. 16**. The incompatibility of more intensive plastic deformation accumulated in the CG phase and less intensive plastic deformation of FG phase then leads to the local concentration of shear deformation between the regions of CG phase and its subsequent intensification. The one measure to mitigate this fracture micromechanism could be better cohesion property of the interface of FG and CG phase, i.e. mitigation of the presence of coarse oxide particles, and mitigation of gradients of intensive plastic deformation within the microstructure, i.e. large distances between the CG regions.

Fig. 15 Relationship between yield strength and uniform elongation of 316L stainless steels prepared with various approaches, literature and present study data.

Fig. 16 The scheme of micromechanism of ductile fracture of bimodal steels.

5. Conclusions

The present study prepared bimodal 316L austenitic steels by combining fine-grained oxide dispersion-strengthened (ODS) steel with coarse-grained austenite steel, compacted using spark plasma sintering. Their microstructure and mechanical properties were analyzed and compared. The following conclusions can be drawn from the results:

- The microstructure of bimodal 316L steel achieved an aspect ratio of ~ 10 between coarse and fine grains, with fine grains maintaining sizes of $1.0\ \mu\text{m}$ and coarse grains refined to $9.8\text{--}10.8\ \mu\text{m}$.
- The fine-grained ODS fraction, prepared by mechanical alloying, was pivotal in stabilizing the microstructure and provided uniform grain size distribution in the final alloy.
- The bimodal steels exhibited a strength-uniform elongation balance compared to unimodal steels, with properties deviating from conventional Hall-Petch trends due to coupling effects between coarse-grained and fine-grained regions.
- The simple mixing approach of milled and non-milled powder successfully combined scalability with high mechanical performance, offering a viable alternative to more complex methodologies such as bimodal milling or high-energy ball milling proposed by other authors.
- The obtained results demonstrate the potential of using fine ODS phase in bimodal microstructures to optimize the strength and ductility of the whole alloy. Future designs may, in addition to improved control of oxygen content, increase coarse grain sizes (e.g., by scaling input powder size and/or heat treatment) to improve mechanical properties in terms of total elongation.

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Declarations

Author contributions

Hynek Hadraba: Conceptualisation, Methodology, Investigation, Writing- Original draft preparation, Writing- Reviewing and Editing; **Ludek Stratil:** Investigation, Writing- Original draft preparation; **Filip Siska:** Investigation, Writing- Original draft preparation; **Zdenek Chlup:** Investigation, Writing- Reviewing and Editing; **Luca Bertolla:** Investigation, Writing- Reviewing and Editing; **Eliska Siska Viragova:** Investigation, Writing- Reviewing and Editing; **Monika Vilemova:** Investigation, Writing- Reviewing and Editing

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data and code availability

Data related to the paper are available in the Zenodo repository with DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14731281

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